

THE STUDY OF LANGUAGE TEACHING APPLICATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT THE LEVEL OF THE WORLD AND UZBEKISTAN

Rakhmonova Maftuna Kakhramon kizi

Abstract: Today, mobile devices play an important role in the lives of the younger generation. In this regard, any use of mobile technologies in the educational process, in particular, when studying at a university, is always perceived positively by students.

Keywords: Independent learning, technology, education, study, mobile learning, society, applications.

INTRODUCTION

Informatization of all spheres of life of modern society has made its own changes in the field of education. At the moment, it is impossible to imagine a lesson in a foreign language without the use of Internet tools, which greatly enrich the educational process. Recently, there has been a transition to a new paradigm of education from “learning for life” to “learning throughout life”, the skills of independent learning activity have become the most demanded skills, as a result of which teachers began to look at the process differently.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of this article is to consider mobile learning as an innovative form of learning, highlight its main characteristics, highlight the most popular mobile applications that a teacher can use in the process of teaching a foreign language¹.

¹ Borshcheva V. V. Mobile learning in teaching foreign languages // Issues of linguodidactics and intercultural communication in the context of modern research: collection of scientific articles of the XI International Scientific and Practical Conference/ resp. ed. N. V. Kormilina, N. Yu. Shugaeva. - Cheboksary, 2019. - P. 149–154.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By mobile learning (m-learning) we mean the use of mobile devices and their didactic capabilities in the learning process. Currently, the number of students who own mobile phones is approaching 100%, so a foreign language teacher should use mobile devices to optimize the process of teaching foreign languages. The main task facing the teacher at the moment is to develop and apply methods for the systematic use of mobile applications in the learning process. At the same time, it is important to motivate students to use their usual mobile devices for educational purposes, give them a clear algorithm for working with the application, and explain the purpose of this type of learning.

Considering mobile learning, we note its main characteristics:

- mobile learning is a person-oriented, situational process that takes place at a convenient time and in a convenient place;
- mobile learning is an innovative process in the education system;
- mobile learning requires conscious effort;
- A distinctive feature of mobile learning is its focus on active independent work.

The use of mobile technologies in the learning process should be based on a systematic approach, ensure the implementation of specific didactic tasks. As the researchers emphasize, one of the important characteristics of mobile technologies is that they help the teacher create a collaborative environment that subsequently leads students to independent learning. This approach represents a fundamental change in the philosophy of teaching and learning, where mobile devices are especially important, as they provide the possibility of instant feedback and assessment, transfer learning interaction to another level of quality.

Considering other advantages of mobile learning, we note gamification, which has already become a trend in modern foreign language education. Gamification is the use of gaming techniques in a non-gaming context in order to increase the interest and motivation of students in learning. This term was first used by British IT expert Nick

Pelling. Undoubtedly, the use of games in the learning process helps to increase motivation and is not a difficult task for a teacher. Mobile applications provide great opportunities for integrating games into the learning process.

Duolingo is one of the popular English learning apps for beginners. Classes are structured in accordance with the chosen topic, the assessment of the quality of assignments is organized. Exercises help students to effectively replenish vocabulary. Duolingo lessons adapt to the individual capabilities of users, allow you to organize feedback. Over two hundred million people around the world use Duolingo. Fun, game-like lessons motivate students' increased interest in learning a foreign language.

The Coursera mobile app (<https://ru.coursera.org/about/mobile>) offering courses with video lectures, self-grading assignments, and discussion forums. According to the students, the most interesting course in the “Specialization” section was the Successful Negotiation course, which consists of 4 blocks²:

- Welcome to Successful Negotiation!
- Plan Your Negotiation Strategy,
- Use Key Tactics for Success,
- Create a Contract.

On the edx.org platform, Using e-mail for networking in English (<https://www.edx.org/course/using-e-mail-for-networking-in-english>) includes writing strategies effective emails with a focus on subject selection, messages for different audiences, greeting formats, presentation format, and email writing practice.

QuillBot is a paraphrasing and summarizing tool that helps millions of students and professionals cut their writing time by more than half using state-of-the-art AI to rewrite any sentence, paragraph, or article.

² Eremin Yu. V., Krylova E. A. The use of mobile technologies in the independent work of students in a foreign language in a non-linguistic university // Bulletin of the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A. I. Herzen. – 2014. – No. 167. - P. 158-166.

CONCLUSION

Thus, taking into account the objective difficulties that need to be overcome when organizing teaching foreign languages in a non-linguistic university - often a low level of foreign language proficiency in university students; low motivation of students in learning a foreign language; insufficient number of hours provided by the curriculum for learning a foreign language at the level required by the current standards; the lack of sufficient technical support for classrooms and educational and methodological material - with the right approach, the use of mobile technologies in students' independent work has more advantages than disadvantages.

REFERENCES

1. Borshcheva V. V. Mobile learning in teaching foreign languages // Issues of linguodidactics and intercultural communication in the context of modern research: collection of scientific articles of the XI International Scientific and Practical Conference/ resp. ed. N. V. Kormilina, N. Yu. Shugaeva. - Cheboksary, 2019. - P. 149–154.
2. Guz Yu. A. Effective use of mobile applications and tablets in teaching a foreign language // Azimut of scientific research: pedagogy and psychology. - T. 6. - No. 4 (21). - 2017. - P. 59–62.
3. Eremin Yu. V., Krylova E. A. The use of mobile technologies in the independent work of students in a foreign language in a non-linguistic university // Bulletin of the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A. I. Herzen. – 2014. –No. 167. - P. 158-166.
4. Klimenko M. V., Sleptsova L. A. Mobile learning in the practice of teaching a foreign language at a university // Bulletin of the Chuvash State Pedagogical University. I. Ya. Yakovleva. - 2016. - No. 4 (92). - P. 118-126.
5. Mirontseva S. S. Pedagogical experiment in the study of the process of teaching future managers a foreign language using electronic educational resources // World of Science, Culture, education. - Gorno-Altai, 2018. - No. 5 (72). - P. 126-128.

6. Novoseltseva N. V. Mobile technologies in the organization of independent work in a foreign language in a non-linguistic university // Bulletin of the Buryat State University university. Pedagogy. Philology. Philosophyfiya. - 2017. - Issue. 1. - P. 172-179.